

Financing Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the map of research developments around financing risks in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The research object is financing risk. The source of data collection comes from searching national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Sinta and Scopus through the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on the order of year, author, and publisher; (2) mapping the results of network visualization and bibliometric trends in scientific publications using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software; and (3) research topic mapping. The research results show that the number of publications has increased significantly yearly. And based on the results of the mapping using the VOSviewer application, research on financing risk is divided into 5 clusters and 85 items. Meanwhile, based on the Library Research results, 7 main themes surround the risk of financing in Islamic and Conventional Banking. The implications and contributions of this study are to map topics often researched by researchers so that they can become references for future researchers.

Keywords: Financing Risk; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic and Conventional Banking.

Introduction

Risk management in banking has improved in line with developments in the financial industry as a whole (Kunz 2021) . In recent years, banks have begun to understand the importance of risk management to maintain business stability and continuity. This can be seen from the existence of regulations from the Financial Services Authority (OJK) which regulate risk exposure management and effective corporate governance (Kulinska-Sadtocha 2022) . Risks in the financial sector must be recognized and controlled by estimating the potential that may occur in the future, not after the risk has already occurred. Therefore, a methodology for modeling risks that may occur in the future is very important so that those making decisions can prepare strategies to overcome future risks (Oyewo 2022) . One of the risks that occur in the financial industry is financing risk. Financing risk management involves identifying, assessing, controlling and monitoring these risks over time to ensure that the bank remains stable and maintains its reputation.

In previous research, there were several financing risks, both in profit sharing financing (Murabahah, Mudharabah, Musyarakah), Ijarah/IMBT, and others. The high risk in financing is reflected in the NPF ratio position which is often referred to as problematic financing. Problematic financing is financing that has not met the bank's targets

such as principal repayment or problematic profit sharing, which has a risk of arising in the future for the bank. Included in problematic financing are special attention, doubtful, bad and current categories that have the potential to be in arrears. The level of financing risk is measured by comparing the Non-Performing Financing/ NPF balance with the total financing as a whole (Izzuddin 2022) . The risk level of musyarakah financing is calculated by comparing the amount of musyarakah financing that experiences problems because returns do not match the agreed schedule, with the total financing as a whole (Warninda, Ekaputra, and Rokhim 2019) . The risk of Ijarah financing in banking is one of the main risks faced by banks. In Ijarah financing, banks act as asset owners and finance business owners (lessees) to obtain benefits from these assets. Ijarah financing risks include credit risk, market risk and operational risk (Halim 2020) . The risk of Qardhul Hasan financing in banking is one of the risks faced by banks in running their business. In financing Qardhul Hasan, banks provide financial assistance without compensation or interest, so the main risk faced is liquidity risk (Al-Melahi 2022) . The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding financing risks in Islamic and conventional banking. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research financing risks.

Based on the problems above, mapping of financing risk management topics is needed to identify, measure and control risks that will occur. This can fulfill the need for human resources tasked with risk management to have knowledge, skills and work attitudes according to the bank's needs. So, the aim of this research is to map research topics around financing risks in Islamic and Conventional Banking using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) Library Research study to analyze, identify and review articles from indexed international journals and accredited national journals.

Literature Review

Financing risk is the risk associated with lending activities by banks to their customers (Ekaputri 2014) . This risk includes the risk that the customer will not be able to repay the loan on time, the risk that the value of the collateral provided by the customer is not sufficient to cover the loan if the customer fails to pay, and the risk that the bank will not be able to obtain the expected profits from the financing (Mutamimah 2022) . Banks must consider various factors such as economic stability, interest rates, and specific industry conditions when determining the level of financing risk and prioritizing financing to customers who have a lower risk profile (Widarjono 2020) .

Bibliometric studies are a branch of science that analyzes and evaluates scientific publications and related information (Hamidah 2020) . It involves the use of statistical and informatics methodologies to assess the production, citation, and dissemination of knowledge in scientific literature (Thakuria 2021) . Bibliometric studies can be used to measure the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions and scientific fields, as well as to understand interactions and relationships

between scientific fields and publications. It can also help in the identification and evaluation of trends and issues in the scientific literature (Shah 2020) . Some applications of bibliometric studies include citation network analysis, cluster analysis, and visibility analysis (M. Kom 2021) . Results from bibliometric studies can be used by researchers, government, and industry to understand developments and contributions in scientific fields and to determine future research directions (Dubyna et al. 2022) .

VOSviewer is bibliometric software used for visualization and analysis of scientific publication data (Nurdin 2021) . It allows users to visualize citation, co-citation, and co-word analysis data in the form of graphs and diagrams that are intuitive and easy to accept (Ninglasari 2021) . VOSviewer can help researchers and analysts carry out citation network analysis, find relationships between scientific fields, and understand trends and issues in scientific literature (Soegoto 2022) . It also helps in determining future research directions and gaining insight into the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions, and scientific fields. VOSviewer has an easy-to-use user interface and can be used together with data coming from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. It allows users to visualize and analyze publication data effectively and efficiently (van Eck NJ 2022) .

Studies Library Research is a process that includes identification, evaluation, and synthesis of results from previous research on a specific topic (Maradin 2021) . It aims to provide an overview of trends, issues, and advances in related fields and assist in understanding how previous research influences future research developments and directions (Sawhney 2021) . Library Research studies are usually conducted as part of the research process to ensure that researchers understand the existing research environment and produce non-duplicative results (Al-Faihani 2020) . It also helps in determining problems and gaps in the existing literature and helps in the formulation of hypotheses and understanding of specific research areas (Kalkavan 2019) . Library Research studies can be carried out by accessing scientific publication databases, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar (Moch 2018) . Researchers can also carry out manual searches through scientific journals and related books. Library Research studies must be carried out with a systematic and objective methodology to ensure that the results are accurate and valid (El-Halaby, Aboul-Dahab, and Bin Qoud 2021) .

Methodology

This research uses quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The object of the research is financing risk. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on financing risks in Islamic and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from search for national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Scopus, and ProQuest via the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals

based on the title words category with the keyword " Financing Risk " within the entire year period (1999 -2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software with a total of 227 data.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics research based on Library Research studies (Budianto and Dewi 2022) .

Results and Discussion

1. Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Financing Risks in Islamic and Conventional Banking

There are 227 international and national journals based on the results of data collection from the Perish/Harzing application during the period 1999 to 2022. There are 49 journals Scopus indexed international. And there is 178 international and national journals indexed by Sinta around financing risk research.

Journal publication data regarding Financing Risk by year

Year	Number of Publications	Reference Source Citation
1999	1	
2004	1	
2005	1	
2008	1	
2009	3	
2010	2	
2012	1	
2014	11	
2015	18	
2016	12	
2017	21	
2018	22	
2019	28	
2020	35	
2021	30	
2022	38	

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 201 6.

2. Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Financing Risks in Islamic and Conventional Banking

There are several things that need to be considered when knowing bibliometric results with software VOSviewer, namely: first, the VOSviewer interface displays diagrams and graphs that visualize publication data. Second, visual components, namely several visual components that may appear in VOSviewer bibliometric results including nodes (representations of publications), lines (representations of citation relationships), and colors (representations of categories or topics). Third, citation network analysis, namely citation network analysis helps in determining relationships between publications and understanding how publications are related to each other. Fourth, cluster analysis, namely cluster analysis helps in determining relationships between topics or fields of science and understanding how publications are related to certain topics or fields of science. Fifth, citation analysis, namely citation analysis helps in determining the most noted publications and understanding how publications are related to each other. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around Financing Risk

Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

Software visualization results VOSViewer is related to the research development map regarding financing risks in Islamic and Conventional Banking, there are 5 clusters and 85 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1, consists of 28 topic items, namely: bmt, business, capital, collateral, contract, customer, documentation, effectiveness, financing risk management, fund, interview, Islamic financial institutions, Jakarta, loss, mudharabah, mudharabah financing, murabahah, murabahah financing, musyarakah, observation, profit sharing, qualitative approach, risk, risk management, risk management strategy, sharia, value.
- Cluster 2, consists of 21 topic items, namely: banks, people's financing banks, sharia banks, sharia commercial banks, bopo, bprs, capital adequacy, third party funds, Indonesia, capital adequacy, liquidity, capital, operational efficiency, financing, financing murabahah, implementation of management, influence of capital adequacy, influence of financing risk, risk, credit risk, financing risk.
- Cluster 3, consists of 20 topic items, namely: assets, Bank Muamalat Indonesia, Bank Syariah Mandiri, capital adequacy ratio, car, deposit ratio, FDR, financing risk, Islamic commercial bank, level, liquidity risk, musyarakah financing, NPF, performing financing, profit, relationship, return, roa, sharia bank, tbk.
- Cluster 4, consists of 11 topic items, namely: commercial bank, credit risk, equity, gcg, good corporate governance, Islamic bank, Islamic banking, loan, profitability, purposive sampling, quality.
- Cluster 5, consists of 5 topic items, namely: financing, Malaysia, management, performance, world bank.

3. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Definition and Objectives of Financing Risk Management

The findings in this research topic include: First, the definition of Financing Risk. Financing risk in banking is the potential loss that may occur to a bank as a result of the failure of the party receiving the financing to fulfill its obligation to repay the loan it receives. In this case, financing risk involves three main things, namely credit risk, liquidity risk and market risk. By understanding financing risks, banks can prepare themselves to face and overcome these risks, so that they can maintain the stability and continuity of their business.

Second, the objectives of Financing Risk management. The aim of financing risk management in banking is to minimize potential losses that may occur in financing, while ensuring that banking can maintain its stability and reliability in the long term. There are several main objectives of financing risk management in banking, including: (1) Preventing losses, namely by identifying, assessing and monitoring financing risks, banks can take action to prevent possible losses; (2) Ensuring long-term stability and reliability, namely financing risk management ensuring that banks can maintain their stability and reliability in the long term, despite economic turmoil or market changes; (3) Maintaining business integrity and reputation, namely financing risk management ensuring that banks do not carry out activities that could harm clients or endanger banking reputation; (4) Ensuring compliance with regulations and regulations, namely financing risk management, ensuring that banks comply with all applicable regulations and rules,

and ensuring that banks operate within permitted limits; (5) Increasing business efficiency, namely by managing financing risks effectively, banks can reduce costs related to financing and expand the financing portfolio.

4. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Financing Risk Monitoring

The findings in this research topic include: First, the authority and responsibilities of the Board of Commissioners. In terms of financing risk management, the Board of Commissioners has several authorities, including: (1) Ensuring that the bank has an effective financing risk management system and ensuring that the system complies with applicable regulations and industry standards; (2) Assess and ensure that bank management has the capacity and competence to manage financing risks; (3) Ensure that banks have adequate procedures and mechanisms to assess and monitor financing risks; (4) Provide recommendations and provide advice to bank management regarding policies and actions taken in managing financing risks; (5) Supervise and ensure that the bank has an effective complaint mechanism and ensures that bank customers can convey their complaints effectively regarding financing risk management; and (6) Ensure that the bank has procedures and mechanisms to ensure that the financing received by the bank is appropriate financing and meets banking security and stability standards. The authority of the Board of Commissioners in managing financing risks may vary between countries and in some countries the Board of Commissioners may have broader or more limited duties and responsibilities compared to the authority described above.

Second, the authority and responsibility of the Board of Directors. The Board of Directors has several main authorities and responsibilities in financing risk, such as: (1) Establishing and supervising financing risk control policies and procedures, including aspects of customer selection, credit risk evaluation, and credit portfolio management; (2) Ensure that the bank has an adequate risk control system, such as a credit information system, credit monitoring system, and financing risk control system; (3) Determine the level of risk that can be accepted by the bank and ensure that the level of risk taken by the bank does not exceed the specified limits; (4) Ensure that the bank has a system for regular monitoring and evaluation of customers' financial conditions and makes wise credit distribution decisions; (5) Supervise and monitor credit risk control policies and practices and ensure that the bank complies with applicable rules and regulations; and (6) Ensure that the bank has competent and adequate human resources to manage financing risks and ensure that the bank has the capacity to overcome possible financing risks. Thus, the Board of Directors holds a major responsibility in ensuring that the bank has an adequate financing risk control system and can ensure that the bank remains stable and successful in the long term.

Third, it relates to Human Resources (HR), which plays an important role in managing financing risks in banking. The following are several things related to human resources and financing risks in banking: (1) Banking employees who have good competence and

knowledge in the field of financing will be better able to manage financing risks well; (2) Banks must have clear and effective systems and procedures to manage financing risks, and employees must understand and comply with these procedures; (3) Appropriate training and development in the financing sector will ensure that employees have the knowledge and skills necessary to manage financing risks well; (4) Effective supervision and monitoring of senior employees in the financing sector will ensure that employees understand and comply with the correct procedures for managing financing risks; (5) A company culture that emphasizes the importance of managing risk effectively will ensure that employees understand its importance and prioritize it in their work; (6) Banks must have a good information technology system to help manage financing risks effectively. Overall, HR plays an important role in managing financing risks in banking. Therefore, banks must ensure that they have quality human resources and ensure that they have a work environment that motivates and helps employees in managing financing risks well.

Fourth, it relates to the Compliance Risk Management Organization, which is the part of an organization that is responsible for identifying, assessing and managing compliance risks. In the banking industry, compliance risk is the risk that a bank will not be able to fulfill applicable regulatory and regulatory obligations, such as banking regulations, information security regulations, and consumer protection regulations. The Compliance Risk Management Organization in banking must establish and monitor appropriate compliance procedures and practices to ensure that the bank meets all applicable regulations and protects the interests of the bank and its consumers. It is also responsible for evaluating the effectiveness of the compliance program and making changes where necessary. Compliance Risk Management organizations in banking must also ensure that banks have appropriate procedures for dealing with reports of violations and ensure that appropriate actions are taken to resolve problems. It should also ensure that the bank has an appropriate compliance training program to ensure that all employees understand and comply with applicable regulations.

5. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Strategy, Risk Level, Policies, Procedures and Limits in Financing Risk Management

The findings in this research topic include: First, Financing Risk management strategy. The following are several financing risk management strategies that can be implemented by banks: (1) Banks must conduct credit analysis on prospective borrowers to determine the ability and adequacy of the borrower's ability to repay the loan; (2) Banks must have a well-diversified portfolio, so that financing risks are distributed evenly and are not concentrated in certain sectors or products; (3) Banks must use sophisticated and integrated information systems to monitor financing risks in real-time and obtain information about borrowers' financial conditions; (4) Banking must strengthen an operational risk management system that is effective and meets regulatory requirements; (5) Banks must use financing instruments that are appropriate to the borrower's risk characteristics and market

conditions; (6) Banks must monitor and evaluate financing portfolios periodically to ensure that risks are controlled and financing remains healthy; and (7) Banks must have strong and adequate liquidity risk management.

Second, the level of risk to be taken (Risk Appetite) and risk tolerance (Risk Tolerance) for financing risks. Risk Appetite is how much risk a company or financial institution, including banking, can accept. This shows how much risk a bank will take in running its business, such as financing projects or making profits from investments. Meanwhile, Risk Tolerance is how much risk consumers or customers can accept in making investments or financing projects. This shows the level of customer resistance to risks that may occur in the investments or financing they make. When financing projects or offering financial products, banks must take into account their customers' Risk Appetite and Risk Tolerance levels. Banks that have a high risk appetite will be more likely to finance projects that have a high level of risk, while banks with a low risk appetite will prefer to finance projects that have a low risk. However, banks must ensure that the financial products they offer are in line with their customers' Risk Tolerance, so that customers are not exposed to unacceptable risks.

Third, Financing Risk policy. To overcome financing risks, banks have various policies and procedures that must be followed, including: (1) Before providing financing, banks must conduct a credit analysis of potential debtors to determine the debtor's ability and suitability to repay the loan; (2) Banks have certain credit requirements that must be fulfilled by debtors before being provided with financing, such as guarantees, collateral and other supporting documents; (3) Banks must monitor and evaluate every financing provided, to ensure that payments are made in accordance with the agreement; (4) Banks must diversify their credit portfolio, namely by increasing the types of businesses and industries financed, so that financing risks are not concentrated in just one type of business or industry; and (5) Banks must monitor and control financing risks continuously, so that immediate action can be taken if changes occur in the credit situation.

Fourth, Financing Risk procedures. The following are general procedures usually carried out by banks in managing financing risks, including: risk identification, namely 1 The first step in managing financing risk is to identify the type of risk associated with financing. These risks can be credit risk, market risk, liquidity risk and interest rate risk. Next, a risk analysis: Once the risks are identified, the bank will carry out an analysis of these risks to determine the level of risk associated with each financing. This analysis involves examining the customer's financial statements, monitoring economic and market developments, and taking into account other factors that may affect the customer's ability to pay for financing. Next, determine the risk level: After the risks have been identified and analyzed, the bank will provide a financing risk level that is appropriate to the customer. This risk level can be low, medium, or high risk level. Next, implement risk controls: The bank will implement risk controls to reduce the level of financing risk. This risk control can take the form of setting financing limits, providing collateral, and requesting regular customer progress reports. Next, monitoring and evaluation: The Bank will periodically monitor and

evaluate financing risks to ensure that the risk controls implemented are still effective and can reduce financing risks.

Fifth, Financing Risk limit. To limit financing risks, banks usually do several things such as: (1) Banks carry out careful credit analysis to ensure that prospective debtors have the ability to pay the required loans; (2) Banks ensure that their financing portfolio is diversified to reduce credit risk; (3) Banks carry out continuous monitoring and evaluation of financing to ensure that they are not too high risk; (4) Banks usually ask for collateral or collateral to limit financing risks; and (5) Banks usually limit the amount of financing provided to one particular debtor or industry to reduce financing risk.

6. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Identification, Monitoring, Control and Financing Risk Information Systems

The findings in this research topic include: First, identify financing risks. To identify financing risks in banking, there are several steps that can be taken, including: (1) Carrying out a comprehensive analysis of the debtor profile, including credit history, income and finances; (2) Conduct an analysis of general economic conditions and how this affects the business sector being financed by the bank; (3) Conduct an analysis of the expected cash flow from financing activities and how this affects the debtor's ability to pay debts; (4) Analyze the debtor's financial ratios, such as the debt to income ratio, quick ratio and solvency ratio; (5) Conduct an analysis of external factors that can influence the debtor's ability to pay debts, such as market changes, government regulations and natural disasters; and (6) Conduct regular monitoring and evaluation of the financing portfolio to ensure that financing risks remain within acceptable limits.

Second, monitoring Financing Risk, namely the process carried out by banks to identify, assess and monitor risks related to the financing provided. This aims to ensure that the bank can minimize potential losses related to financing and ensure the bank's financial health remains stable. The financing risk monitoring process includes several stages, including: (1) The stage that involves identifying risks related to financing, such as credit risk, market risk and operational risk; (2) The stage that involves assessing the risks that have been identified, namely by determining the level of risk associated with each financing; (3) The stage that involves continuous monitoring of risks related to financing. This includes monitoring financing performance and monitoring the level of risk associated with each financing; and (4) The stage involving the implementation of risk control measures required to ensure that risks related to financing can be controlled and managed properly.

Third, Financing Risk control, namely the process used to minimize risks related to financing activities carried out by banks. There are several methods that can be used to control financing risk, including: Credit analysis, namely banks must carry out adequate analysis before providing financing to customers. This analysis includes customer financial analysis, business analysis and environmental analysis. Next, portfolio diversification, namely banks must diversify their financing

portfolio so that they are not exposed to one type of large risk. Next is credit monitoring and evaluation, namely banks must monitor and evaluate the credit provided periodically to determine developments in customers' conditions and take appropriate action if necessary. Next, capital capability, namely the bank must ensure that its capital level is adequate to overcome losses that may occur from the financing provided. Next, an internal control system, namely the bank must have a good internal control system to ensure that the financing process is carried out correctly and in accordance with applicable procedures. Next, a credit insurance, namely the bank may also consider taking out credit insurance to overcome the risks associated with financing.

Fourth, the Financing Risk Management Information System/SIMAR, which is a system used by banks to identify, evaluate and manage financing risks. The aim of SIMAR is to ensure that the financing provided by banks has a controlled risk level and meets banking policy standards. SIMAR carries out a monitoring process for all financing activities carried out by banks, including monitoring financing recipients, types of financing, and levels of financing risk. With this information, banks can make better decisions about resource allocation and prioritize financing that has low risk potential. SIMAR can also help banks manage financing risk by monitoring and analyzing data, such as debt ratios and cash flows, to predict future risk levels. Basically, SIMAR is an important tool for banks to control financing risks and ensure that banks have controlled risk levels and comply with banking standards.

Fifth, the Financing Risk Internal Control System (Internal Control System for Loan Risk), namely the procedures and actions carried out by a banking company to ensure that financing risks can be controlled and managed effectively. The main objective of this system is to ensure that financing activities are carried out safely and efficiently, as well as ensuring that bank assets remain protected and their value is stable. The following are several things related to the internal control system for financing risk in banking, namely risk identification, namely the first step in managing financing risk is to identify existing risks. This can include credit risk, market risk, liquidity risk, and operating risk. Next, a risk analysis, that is, once the risks are identified, the bank must carry out a risk analysis to determine the different levels of risk and determine how to manage them. Next, strategic planning, namely the bank must have a clear strategic plan to manage financing risks and ensure that bank assets remain protected. Next, the financing process, namely the financing process must be carried out carefully and through strict procedures. This includes credit evaluation and verification of information received from potential borrowers. Next, monitoring and evaluation, namely banks must monitor and evaluate financing performance regularly to ensure that financing risks can be controlled and managed effectively. Information system, namely the bank must have a good information system to help manage and monitor financing risks.

7. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Financing Risk Measurement

There are several method findings in this research topic, including: First, Loan-to-Value (LTV) Ratio, which is the ratio used by banks to assess the level of risk in financing. LTV Ratio measures the comparison between the loan amount provided by the bank to customers and the value of the property pledged as collateral. The higher the LTV Ratio, the greater the risk for the bank because the loan amount given is relatively larger than the value of the property collateral. Therefore, banks will usually only provide loans with a relatively low LTV Ratio to reduce the risk of payment failure. LTV Ratio is usually used as one of the factors considered in the financing decision making process. Banks will consider other factors such as the customer's financial stability, credit history and business prospects, before deciding to provide a loan.

Second, the Debt Service Coverage Ratio (DSCR), which is a ratio used to assess the ability of a company or project to repay loans taken within a predetermined time. DSCR is used by banks and financial institutions to assess financing risks and decide whether to provide loans or not. DSCR is calculated by dividing net income after tax (EBITDA) by the sum of interest payments and loan installments. A higher DSCR value indicates that the company or project has greater income compared to debt payments. Generally, banks and financial institutions require a DSCR of around 1.2 to 1.5 to provide loans. This means that the company or project must have sufficient income to pay interest and debt installments and maintain net profit after tax.

Third, Risk-Weighted Assets (RWA), which is a method used by banks to measure and control financing risk. This method takes into account the risk of each bank asset position and assigns a risk weight to each asset. This risk weight is used to determine the amount of capital that must be maintained by the bank to cover the risks associated with these assets. The RWA implementation process begins with a risk assessment for each bank asset position. This risk is then classified into credit risk, market risk and operational risk. After that, each asset position is given a risk weight that corresponds to the level of risk associated with that asset. This risk weight is based on applicable regulations, such as Basel III which provides guidelines on how to determine the risk weight for each type of asset. This risk weight is then used to calculate RWA, namely by dividing the total assets by the risk weight applied to those assets. The results of the RWA calculation are used to determine the amount of capital that must be maintained by the bank. This capital is used to cover risks associated with bank assets and ensure that the bank has the ability to overcome losses if unfavorable economic conditions occur.

Fourth, Credit Scoring, which is a method used by banks to assess risks in providing financing. This method uses statistical analysis and algorithms to estimate the probability of payment failure by a potential debtor. The credit scoring process involves collecting data about potential debtors, such as credit history, income, employment, and other financial information. This data is then analyzed using an algorithm to determine a credit score, which describes the level of risk associated with the financing. Banks can use credit scores to make decisions about whether to provide financing and on what terms. For example, a prospective debtor with a higher credit score may be allowed to borrow money at a lower interest rate or longer term. On the other hand,

prospective borrowers with low credit scores may only be allowed to borrow money at higher interest rates and shorter terms. Credit scoring helps banks to make more informative and objective decisions in providing financing. This method also helps banks to reduce the risk of payment failure and speed up the process of providing financing. However, this method also has several disadvantages, such as discrimination against potential debtors with limited or unrepresentative credit data.

Other methods, namely: Mashlahah, Maqashid Syariah, Auto Regressive Distributed Lag/ARDL, Decision Support System /DSS, Credit Scoring, Creditrisk, community characteristics.

8. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Financing Risk Mitigation

Mitigating financing risk in banking is an effort to reduce potential losses that could occur as a result of financing carried out by banks. The main objective is to minimize the risk of possible losses and ensure that the bank remains in a stable position and has sufficient resilience to overcome these potential losses. Several ways to mitigate financing risk in banking include: (1) Banks can increase the diversification of their financing portfolio by spreading risk across various economic and geographic sectors; (2) Banks must carry out adequate credit risk assessments before providing financing to prospective debtors; (3) Banks must ensure that good risk management and corporate governance practices are implemented in financing activities; (4) Banks must continue to monitor and evaluate the financing portfolio and take necessary actions to overcome potential risks; (5) Banks must have an effective credit risk management system to ensure that financing risks can be controlled and managed effectively.

There are several methods of mitigating financing risk, including: (1) Home Ownership Financing/PPR risk; (2) financing risk with the 5C principle (Character, Capacity, Capital, Collateral, Condition); (3) financing risk with the 7P principles (Personality, Purpose, Party, Payment, Prospect, Profitability, Protection); (4) financing risk using the POAC principle (Planning, Organizing, Actuating, Controlling); (5) vehicle ownership financing risks; (6) financing risks for underprivileged communities; (7) risks of financing the Countercyclical Covid-19 policy; (8) Short-term and long-term estimates.

9. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Determinants of Financing Risk

Determinants of Financing Risk are factors that influence the possibility of losses in financing received by the bank. In the banking world, financing risks are very important to pay attention to because they can affect the bank's financial performance and require action to overcome these risks.

There are several determinants of financing risk in this research topic, including: (1) Macroeconomics; (2) Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR; (3) Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR; (4) Operational Expenses to Operational Income/BOPO; (5) Return On Assets /ROA; (6) Return On

Equity /ROE; (7) BI Rate; (8) Good Corporate Governance /GCG; (9) financial crisis; (10) financing expansion; (11) liquidity; (12) quality of financing; (13) Industrial Production Index /IPI; (14) Real Sales Index/IPR; (15) Natural Certainty Contracts; (16) Natural Uncertainty Contracts; (17) Non-Performing Financing /NPF; (18) capital adequacy; (19) Accounts Officer; (20) Linkage; (21) Fintech; (22) asset growth; (23) solvency; (24) total asset turnover; (25) currency exchange rates; (26) Non Performing Financing /NPF; (27) bank size; (28) Gross Domestic Product/GDP; (29) insurance; (30) number of customers; (31) gold pawn; (32) MSMEs; (33) liquidity; (34) company characteristics; (35) sharia governance.

10. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Problems and Influence of Financing Risk

There are several influences on financing risk in banking, including: (1) Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR; (2) economic growth; (3) Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR; (4) Non-Performing Financing /NPF; (5) Return On Assets /ROA; (6) Return On Equity /ROE; (7) Sharia Compliance; (8) margins; (9) Profit Distribution Management; (10) Third Party Funds/DPK; (11) Net Interest Margin /NIM; (12) return of customer financing; (13) number of customers; (14) efficiency level; (15) MSME contribution; (16) liquidity.

There are several problems in financing risk, including: (1) sharia pawnshops; (2) agricultural sector; (3) working capital; (4) venture capital; (5) gold installments; (6) DSN-MUI fatwa regarding financing risks; (7) problematic financing; (8) risk management of Mudharabah, Murabahah (Bil Wakalah), Musyarakah (Mutanaqishah), Ijarah, Istishna, Qardh financing; (9) financing risk in fraudulent investments; and (10) financing risks based on a philosophical review.

1 1. Gap Research Mapping around Financing Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking

VOSviewer bibliometric mapping (in Figure 1) and Library Research mapping, there are 6 things that can be considered for mapping gap research around financing risks in Islamic and conventional banking, including: first, financing portfolio analysis. This analysis can help banks understand the risks in their financing portfolio and identify the sectors most vulnerable to risk. In this analysis, you can pay attention to the type of financing distributed by banks, for example consumer credit, small and medium business credit, or corporate credit. how these risks can affect banking financial health.

Second, evaluate credit quality. Credit quality evaluation can help banks identify loans that have the potential to become bad or problematic. This analysis can include checking the quality of collateral taken by the bank, such as collateral or mortgages, as well as evaluating the debtor's ability to repay the credit.

Third, risk management strategy. It is important for banks to have an effective risk management strategy to reduce financing risks. It explores the strategies banks use, such as credit portfolio diversification,

use of derivative financial instruments, and use of data analysis technology.

Fourth, developing a risk model. Developing a risk model can help banks to predict financing risks and take appropriate preventive actions. This risk model can include factors such as economic conditions, interest rates, and inflation rates.

Fifth, a comparative study of financing risks between countries. This is done by conducting a comparative study of financing risks between countries. This study can be carried out by comparing financing risk policies, risk management practices, and the effectiveness of internal control systems in the banking sector in various countries. This can provide useful insight in efforts to mitigate financing risks in banking.

Sixth, technology development for financing risk management. This can be done by developing technology for financing risk management in banking. This technology can be in the form of a decision support system, data analysis application, or security technology to prevent fraud or detrimental actions.

Conclusions and Advice

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, the number of research publications regarding financing risks in Islamic and Conventional Banking during the period 1999 to 2022, shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 227 research articles. Second, in mapping visualization using the VOS viewer, research developments regarding financing risks in Islamic and Conventional Banking are divided into 5 clusters and 85 items. Cluster 1 consists of 28 items, cluster 2 consists of 21 items, cluster 3 consists of 20 items, cluster 4 consists of 11 items, cluster 5 consists of 5 items. Third, based on a Library Research, there are 8 main research themes regarding financing risks in Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely: (1) Definition and objectives of risk management; (2) Risk monitoring; (3) Strategy, risk level, policies, procedures, limits; (4) Identification, monitoring, control, information systems; (5) Risk measurement; (6) Risk mitigation; (7) Risk determinants; and (8) Risk issues and impacts.

The implication and contribution of this research is to map topics that are often researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers. The limitation of this research is that it has not mapped financing risks in Islamic and conventional banking.

Suggestions for further research are to use more data samples, so that they can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limited data samples in this research and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained: First, it is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization. Second, the results of the Library Research study can be explained in a more complex way.

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